

Robotic Grape Inspection and Selective Harvesting in Vineyards

Sotiris Stavridis, Leonidas Droukas, Zoe Doulgeri, Dimitrios Papageorgiou, Fotios Dimeas, Ángel Soriano, Sergi Molina, Sami Ahmed Deiri, Michael Hutchinson, Jaime Pulido-Fentanes, Ibrahim Hroob, Riccardo Polvara, Marc Hanheide, Grzegorz Cielniak, Nikiforos Samarinas, Dimitrios Kateris, Dionysis Bochtis, Georgia Peleka, Stefanos Papadam, Dimitra Triantafyllou, Alexios Papadimitriou, Christos Papadopoulos, Ioannis Mariolis, Dimitrios Giakoumis, Dimitrios Tzovaras

Abstract—Driven by the increasing food demand and the need for higher-quality cultivation, precision agriculture grows steadily during the last decade. It involves the application of mobile robots and intelligent robotic technologies in various agricultural field tasks, concerning a variety of crop types. Aiming at compensating for the lack of selective robotic harvesting solutions regarding the high-value crop of grapes, the EU-funded project BACCHUS¹ develops an intelligent mobile robotic system, comprising two independent and cooperative robots: one for the grape inspection and collection of valuable data regarding their maturity level, and one for the bimanual harvesting of grapes in a human-inspired manner. Validated via real-field trials, the proposed autonomous system pushes forward the precision agriculture application for a particularly sensitive crop type in the challenging and heavily cluttered environment of vineyards, facilitating the selective harvesting of high-quality grapes.

Index Terms—Robotics and Automation in Agriculture and Forestry, Bimanual Manipulation, Computer Vision for Automation

I. INTRODUCTION

WITH the climate change and growing population, agricultural productivity growth is unlikely to meet the increased demand for food². Given the pressure on labor availability caused by the demographics of an aging population, in addition to the increasing urbanization and limitations on available arable land, precision agriculture supplemented by advanced agricultural technologies and intelligent robotics needs to be enabled to alleviate a foreboding food crisis. The incorporation of these technologies into the agricultural production will not only benefit productivity, but also improve the difficult working conditions of farmers, laborers and vehicle operators.

Mobile robots application and implementation of robotics and automation technology in agriculture are constantly increasing, with various field tasks and operations under consideration, including selective harvesting, transplanting/seeding, pruning/thinning, weed control, crop health/disease monitoring, and yield estimation. Given the large number of tasks ripe for automation, research projects, literature works and innovation-driven companies are providing robotic solutions for many aspects of these agricultural functions, and developing the required technologies such as mapping and navigation

methodologies, vision algorithms for crop and weed detection as well as maturity estimation and disease identification, yield prediction strategies and so on [1]. Robotic harvesting in particular has attracted significant research attention, basically due to the hardware design process and algorithm characteristics challenges with regard to the harvested crops. Various crops have been considered as robotic harvesting targets, including sweet peppers, apples, tomatoes, strawberries, and melons. Smart, automated, and selective harvesting provides an improvement in production leaving the unripe products in the field to mature. However, in order to realise such automation, constant progress is required regarding the cognitive and mechatronic capabilities of the robotic agents replacing the human workers in these tasks, especially in cases of delicate crops like grapes where human-like harvesting actions are required.

In this context, the EU project BACCHUS develops an autonomous robotic ecosystem targeting the high-value crop of wine grapes and contributing to the previously under-explored area of selective robotic grape harvesting. Vineyards comprise a significantly challenging environment, with grape bunches being a very sensitive crop of no standard shape/size that is difficult to detect since its color is quite similar to its background/surrounding. Additionally, wine grape vineyards, which use a vertical trellis rather than a pergola set-up, are heavily cluttered environments. In these cases, grapes are surrounded by a variety of obstacles (e.g. leaves, branches, irrigation pipes etc) that may occlude fully or partially both the bunches and their stems which together with the variable lighting conditions hinder the overall harvesting procedure. To address these issues, the BACCHUS system employs two different, cooperative mobile platforms: (a) the inspection Mobile Robotic Platform (iMRP), responsible for the intelligent grape inspection, and (b) the harvesting Mobile Robotic Platform (hMRP), responsible for the selective grape harvesting. To achieve their goals, both platforms are equipped with a large variety of sensors for navigation and inspection, whereas the hMRP additionally involves a dual-arm robotic manipulator enhanced with tools, sensors, and specialised grippers, with the latter generated through additive manufacturing to adapt to the size of the crop. The intelligent inspection of grapes is performed via the iMRP, navigating through the field, mapping both the vineyard and the grape bunches, while actively inspecting the latter and providing the human operator

¹<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871704> & <https://bacchus-project.eu/>

²https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/sites/www.un.org.development.desa.pd/files/undesapd_2021_e_cn.9_2021_2_advanceunedited.pdf

with various useful data regarding grape maturity level and yield predictions. To overcome the surrounding occlusions and obstacles that may significantly hinder the harvesting process, the hMRP employs a human-inspired, bimanual approach: firstly, the grape's stem is visually unveiled by one arm equipped with an in-hand camera and a cutting tool (camera arm) and subsequently the grape is grasped and manipulated by the other arm with a gripper (grasping arm) to create or increase further the stem's cutting affordances, i.e. the available free space for the cutter placement, and thus the grape's detachment from its branch.

While most existing grape robotic solutions concern only inspection operations (e.g. health/maturity monitoring, yield prediction) [1], the BACCHUS two-robot system couples the above functions with that of selective harvesting, thus providing a complete agricultural solution regarding the high-value crop of wine grapes. Partitioning the inspection and harvesting operations into two different robots reduces each robot's hardware and software complexity as well as the computational load of their respective control methodologies. In addition, it provides the farmers with the opportunity to carry out multiple tasks simultaneously, decreasing time consumption and increasing productivity e.g. determine maturity levels in one vineyard area while at the same time harvesting already identified ripe grapes in another area. Moreover, each robotic platform can be marketed separately according to the specific needs of the customers, rendering the overall system's exploitation more flexible.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section II describes the two BACCHUS robotic platforms, Section III presents the overall system's modules and their functions, Section IV shows the BACCHUS performance during validation trials performed in a real vineyard and lastly Section V concludes and discusses the BACCHUS project's findings.

II. THE BACCHUS SYSTEM

The BACCHUS proposed solution involves a multi-sensory robotic ecosystem incorporating advanced cognitive capabilities for grape inspection and bimanual selective harvesting. The overall system aims at autonomously operating in the following levels: i) performing robot navigation with quality performance guarantee for grape inspection, weed detection, and data collection via an embedded sensorial system (iMRP); ii) performing bimanual harvesting with human-inspired finesse using a dual-arm robotic platform (hMRP), iii) employing additive manufacturing for adjusting the robot gripper to different grape varieties/sizes and iv) presenting cognitive capabilities and decision-making skills.

A. Inspection Mobile Robotic Platform (iMRP)

The iMRP, depicted in Figure 1-(a), is based on the Thorvald platform - a modular, general purpose, lightweight, and flexible robot system designed to address multiple robotics applications in agricultural environments. The platform is equipped with a variety of sensors, including: two ZED2 stereoscopic RGB cameras (at the platform front and left side) for dense grape mapping/detection and one more ZED2i stereoscopic

Fig. 1: BACCHUS robotic platforms. (a) inspection Mobile Robotic Platform (iMRP). (b) Left: harvesting Mobile Robotic Platform (hMRP) with red basket attached on the platform's front. Right top: Camera arm with cutter and mounted in-hand camera. Right bottom: Grasping arm with specialised gripper.

camera placed at the platform left side and tilted accordingly for weed detection between vine trunks with the ZED cameras selected as a reliable and low-cost solution in outdoor conditions; one Cubert FirefEYE S185 Hyperspectral camera for grape maturity estimation (at the platform rear) which being a snap shot sensor is suitable for autonomous moving platforms in contrast to push-broom ones; two SICK MRS1000 LiDAR sensors (platform front left and rear right) and one Ouster OS1-16 3D LiDAR sensor (platform top) for SLAM, sparse mapping, localization and navigation purposes; lastly, an RTK GNSS receiver with two antennas for global localization. The robot uses machine learning and sensorial information to interpret grape status and qualitative characteristics, utilized in extracting harvesting decisions. A battery of 70 Ah is included with an estimated autonomy of 6 hours.

B. Harvesting Mobile Robotic Platform (hMRP)

The hMRP, depicted in Figure 1-(b) is a light-weight, dual-arm mobile robot with an omnidirectional mobile platform. One of its arms, i.e. the camera arm, carries a stereo in-hand camera together with an electrical cutting tool for grape stem cutting, while the other arm, i.e. the grasping arm, is equipped with an autonomous Robotiq 2F-85 gripper for grape grasping. The gripper's two 3d-printed fingertips are designed so that they envelop the target grape bunch for more stable grasping and are changeable to suit the different grape varieties shapes, sizes and bunch dimensions. The overall platform is equipped with: two UR10e arms for bimanual harvesting; three ZED2 stereo cameras for grape detection (one at the platform front under the red basket, two at the platform left and right sides), which, as in iMRP case, are selected as a

Fig. 2: BACCHUS conceptual modules architecture. Single-direction arrows symbolise one-way flow of information/data, while bidirectional arrows symbolise an exchange of information/data between the involved modules.

reliable outdoor solution with sufficient depth accuracy for robot navigation, obstacle and grape detection; one RealSense D405 stereo camera mounted upon the camera arm’s end-effector for the visual unveiling of the target grape’s stem and vision guided stem reaching, which is selected for its narrow baseline that allows depth estimation from closer distances (up to 10 cm), an essential feature in the aforementioned tasks; two 2D SICK outdoorScan3 safety laser scanners (at platform front left and rear right corners) and a GPS RTK sensor for navigation/localization (at the platform rear left corner). The platform is powered by a battery of 60Ah with an estimated autonomy of 6 hours.

III. BACCHUS OPERATION AND FUNCTIONALITY MODULES

To fulfill its functional goals, BACCHUS incorporates a variety of modules, that are linked to the system’s operational requirements. The conceptual interconnection of these modules is depicted in Figure 2, describing the BACCHUS system’s architecture.

The *Data Management & Operations Planning Support* is the administrative module, that via the *Visualization & GUI* communicates with the human operator allowing to schedule and control the system’s overall functions, providing them also with useful information such as yield predictions as well as important data about e.g. the robots status and location in the vineyards or the progress of harvesting/inspection tasks. This administrative module is the heart of the BACCHUS system, responsible for: a) storing all data that the BACCHUS system utilizes and requires (e.g. maturity spectral libraries, gripper finger designs for the hMRP arm gripper manufacturing, grape/vineyard mappings etc.); b) coordinating and commanding all other modules for the successful BACCHUS core operations execution i.e. the navigation of both platforms in the field (*3D Mapping, Localization & Navigation* module), the grape maturity identification (*Crop Maturity Assessment* module), the grape monitoring and mapping along with weed detection (*Crop Monitoring & Weed Detection* module) and the bimanual harvesting of grapes (*Bimanual Control - Grape Harvesting* module).

In a nutshell, the BACCHUS application initiates with the iMRP, autonomously navigating through the vineyard, monitoring and mapping grapes, in addition to weed detecting (*Crop Monitoring & Weed Detection* module). Equipped with a Hyperspectral camera, the iMRP assesses the maturity level of the inspected grapes and deciphers important information regarding them, such as their sugar content concentration (*Crop Maturity Assessment* module). The *Data Management & Operations Planning Support* module gathers all collected data from inspection and provides valuable information to the human operator regarding yield predictions, while helping them in organising more efficiently the harvest scheduling. Following this schedule, the hMRP navigates inside the field, arriving in front of a harvesting target grape. Then, the harvesting procedure begins, following a human-inspired, bimanual process that involves both the platform’s arms motion in a coordinated manner (*Bimanual Control - Grape Harvesting* module), with one arm responsible for cropping & inspection (camera arm) and the other for grapes grasping & collection (grasping arm). The grasping arm grasps the target crop with its specialized gripper (*Gripper Design & Grasp Planning* module) and manipulates it accordingly to facilitate further its stem cutting by the other arm’s cutting tool. The following subsections describe in detail the various functionality modules, mentioned above (Figure 2), in addition to the developed methodologies/control schemes these modules incorporate.

A. Data Management & Operations Planning Support

This module is responsible for the collection, storage and management of all the available data the BACCHUS system gathers during its functioning. Specifically, the module involves two databases: an SQL database, containing information for the human users, vineyard tasks and areas; and the Firebase Realtime database (an online NoSQL real-time database), storing all data generated by the robots and their various sensors and cameras, that may be required and utilized by other modules of the BACCHUS system. The gathered data can include navigation nodes and maps, localization data, grape maturity spectral libraries, gripper finger designs, task scenarios, detected vine trunks, grape bunches position and volume etc. Additional to data management, the module also

assess and process some of these data in order to offer valuable insights to human operators for yield prediction and operations planning.

To provide estimation for the weight of a bunch and by extension for the overall yield, linear regression models are created for a variety in the following way. Several reference grape bunches are marked and their RGBD images are captured. After their detection in the RGB images and in conjunction with depth information, the grape's area in 3D space is calculated. These reference grape bunches are harvested and weighted and the regression model that correlates the grape bunch's 3D area to the weight is created. Thus, the module is able to estimate the overall yield of a specific variety by summing the regression model's output for each detected grape bunch.

The module can also organise automatically the vineyard's operations (e.g. harvesting, inspection, irrigation of specific areas) in an efficient and productive manner. To achieve this, it supports two levels of scheduling, the offline and the online. In particular, the offline scheduling optimizes in terms of timeline the assignment of the vineyard operations to the appropriate actors, i.e., workers and robots, while taking into account their constraints (e.g., sufficient battery levels for operation completion, avoid scheduling inspection tasks when temperature exceeds the operation range of the hyperspectral cameras' temperature limits etc.). To address this challenge, the mixed-integer programming approach is used since it is a method that provides optimal solutions while it allows the easy addition of constraints. Apart from organizing in an optimal manner the order of the operations, the offline level also tries to minimise the duration of the robotic operations through path optimization. To achieve it, an annealing simulation approach to the traveling salesman problem is developed ensuring both duration and battery optimization.

The online scheduling occurs during the real time execution of the offline schedule and aims to handle deviations in an optimal manner. In this case, any activities which cannot be completed within the a priori calculated time are adapted so that the remaining time is exploited in an optimal manner (e.g. so that the robot harvests as many grape bunches as it can in a limited amount of time). Such cases can be caused due to various unforeseen reasons, such as unexpected low battery alerts or bad weather conditions that require the robot's withdrawal from the field within a timeframe. To achieve the online scheduling, the max-min ant colony optimization approach from [2] is used since it shows the best performance among similar methods, presenting the highest profit for the same time durations.

B. Visualization & GUI

The *Visualization & GUI* module is built as a user-friendly web application for Human-Machine Interaction (HMI). It is developed as a single-page application using the Angular framework and provides numerous functionalities in an intuitive way to the operator (Figure 6). Using web services through APIs, the user can receive weather forecasts or supervise the robots on the field in real-time through

Google Maps satellite images. Moreover, Google Maps of the vineyard area is integrated and a lot of effort is put into enhancing its resolution through drone imaging and tile integration into the Google Maps API. By providing the high-resolution upgrade, the user has a better experience interacting with the BACCHUS system and higher accuracy in marking areas in the map, understanding better the robots' location, or visualising more clearly the estimated yield density along the vineyard rows of the map. The interface provides 3D visualization of the robots and their surroundings in real-time, as well as a live video feed from the robots cameras through appropriate ROS JavaScript libraries. After the inspection of a particular area of the vineyard is complete, the user can visualise the inspection results stored in the online database (*Data Management & Operations Planning Support* module) and receive information about grape maturation status and yield estimates according to the preferred maturation levels. The operator can also manually schedule robot and worker activities in specific areas in the vineyard, while receiving suggestions via the *Data Management & Operations Planning Support* module, that cooperates closely with *Visualization & GUI* for the overall system's administration.

C. 3D Mapping, Localization & Navigation

This module regards the building of maps and robot localization for path planning, as well as navigation of the platforms inside the vineyard. The BACCHUS system utilizes topological maps [3] as the unifying representation to facilitate the navigation of both platforms (iMRP and hMRP) and to be integrated with the rest of the architecture. While individual robots in this heterogeneous fleet have specific implementations of their kinematic design, sensor equipment, navigation constraints, and respective derived tasks and abilities, the abstraction of the current overall system's operational status in a topological representation allows for an efficient state representation of large-scale environments and offers the scalable and efficient operation of the entire fleet. An example of a topological map being used in Ktima Gerovassiliou, Greece (the BACCHUS trial site) can be seen in Figure 3. The advantages of topological maps in large outdoor environments are various since such representation: a) makes global planning more efficient as the path is calculated using only the topological graph instead of the widely used occupancy map which can contain millions of cells; b) can provide semantics stored in the topological nodes and edges to enable to specific

Fig. 3: Topological map from Ktima Gerovassiliou, Greece. Green arrows: node location & orientation. Red polygons: nodes' influence zone. Multicolored lines: edges connecting pair of nodes, with each color describing a different robot navigation behaviour (white for corridor traversal, red for corridor change, black for default navigation).

robot behavior to better adapt to the context where the robot is navigating (e.g. outside vs inside the corridor, types of terrain, one-way navigation, etc.) and c) allows high-level coordination between multiple robots.

The aforementioned topological maps are usually built manually by placing the nodes in a 2d occupancy map previously built with the robot and a 2d lidar or by driving the robot where the nodes' locations need to be placed. While this is a perfectly valid solution for certain scenarios, the system is not very scalable when this has to be done in a 100ha vineyard with hundreds of vine rows. Thus, in an attempt to reduce the initial deployment time and human involvement, the BACCHUS system includes a pipeline to use UAV (drone) imagery as an input to speed up the process to create the topological map of the vineyard [4]. UAV can perform an initial coverage of the field much faster than a ground robot and also offers the possibility to obtain 3D point cloud of the environment. The pipeline contains three main steps: (i) obtain a non-traversable map of the environment, (ii) a classification step to separate vine rows from other structures and (iii) compute the topological nodes and edges. Specifically:

- i) Using the UAV imagery acquired, a 3d point cloud is generated using photogrammetry. Then, a filter is applied to extract the non-ground points and transform those points into a binary image containing everything in the environment that should not be traversable by the robot.
- ii) Each bunch in the binary image coming from the previous step is classified as row/non-row using the variance ratio between the two first Principal Components. Then for every bunch classified as a vine row, a line is fitted using the Hough transform, obtaining the start and end location of each row.
- iii) Using the row lines obtained, a set of topological nodes are computed for the corridors on both sides of the vine row. All rows are masked using the lines and a skeletonisation process is applied to the remaining free space. The skeleton is then transformed into a graph in which the nodes are used as topological nodes. Lastly, all the nodes are transformed into map coordinates and the edges between node pairs are computed.

BACCHUS also explores two possible approaches, to deal with the severe challenges that seasonal changes induce, regarding the robot's localization. The first proposes LTS-Net [5], an end-to-end self-supervised learning model. The approach is data-driven and implicitly learns the long-term stable features by means of a neural network based on PointNet++ [6]. The training data are generated in an unsupervised way by having multiple observations of the same environment taken at different times and producing a pointwise labeling representing each point's long-term stability. The network is a regression model trained by using the stability score as a training signal. This approach has been trained and tested using the BLT dataset [7], created by recorded data at Ktima Gerovassiliou over multiple months. Regarding the session recorded in June, filtered and raw maps are employed for testing localization performance while using FAST-LIO [8], recording an improvement in the Absolute Pose Error from

0.16 m to 0.07 m and the RMSE from 0.17 m to 0.08 m when using the filtered map. The biggest LTS-Net advantage is its ability to extract only those features, stable across time (e.g. poles, trunks), removing from the map the points belonging to grass and leaves. Thus, it is possible not only to improve the localization accuracy but also to reuse existing maps built in a different season, saving time and cost.

The second approach [9] involves a visual Graph-SLAM with a loop closure detection (LCD) strategy enforced with instance segmentation of the trunk regions. The pipeline generates a pool of salient visual features that characterize a scene across time, which are used for LCD and optimization of the pose graph. Specifically, ORB features are calculated on the trunk regions' mask, generated by the Mask R-CNN [10], the descriptor of which represents the visual word. The Bag of Visual Words is formulated by the accumulation of individual visual words and can be searched in a probabilistic manner to detect loop closures and localize the robot in the pose-graph. The network has been trained on manually annotated data, collected during different seasons in Ktima Gerovassiliou.

Empirical analysis through in-field trials demonstrates that the LTS-Net approach outperforms the second approach, resulting in improved localization metrics. For example, the average Absolute Pose error across the sessions when using LTS-Net to filter dynamic points and localize using stable points is 0.35 m, compared to around 0.6 m for the second approach. However, the proposed visual Graph-SLAM approach still achieves more than 50% loop closure detection in all experiments, indicating its potential for further development. To facilitate deployment on different platforms, a dockerized version of the related software has been developed (https://github.com/ibrahimhroob/lts_filter).

D. Crop Monitoring & Weed Detection

The crop monitoring component of this module is responsible for identifying and recognizing grape bunches inside the vineyard. BACCHUS robots are aware of their place in the field and their relative location to the vines by monitoring the field environment and using a dynamically modified 3D environment model provided by the system's crop environment modeling engine, as well as, the position and condition of crops and plants. Mapping of grapes by the *Crop Monitoring* module is performed several times to keep the grape bunches' properties updated in the database (e.g., their location in the map, associated trunk, maturity levels etc.). For this, the iMRP passes through the vineyard multiple times, using the vineyard's map generated by the previous *3D Mapping, Localization & Navigation* module for both robots navigation and localization in the field. The identification of the crops is performed by the BACCHUS perception framework, which consists of two sub-modules: 1) the semantic scene and instance segmentation sub-module which utilizes a scene segmentation model [11] to extract all the information required for manipulating the identified crops (e.g detection of the various components of interest in a vine tree, such as grape bunches, stems, leaves, irrigation pipes, etc.), and 2) the grape/stem detection sub-module [11], which produces the

required 3D poses of the detected crops with respect to the global 3D environment coordinate system.

Utilizing the ZED2i stereo camera at the iMRP left side (Figure 1-(a)) that is sufficiently tilted for viewing the ground between vine trunks, the weed detection component assists in vineyard weed control by detecting and mapping intra-row and inter-row path weed growth. For intra-row path weed detection, two algorithms have been developed and tested. The first algorithm is a Single Shot Detector (SSD) with a ResNet 101 as a backbone while the second algorithm is the Mask RCNN. Python3.7, OpenCV and TensorFlow1.5 are used for both algorithms. The final implementation of the intra-row path weeds detection took place with the development of the Mask RCNN, based on the results of early stopping. As a result, the developed model performs highly accurately in cases where the weeds have distinct borders, while in cases where there are no distinct boundaries between the weeds, the model performs adequately [12]. The RCNN model consistently shows higher accuracy and precision for all tested grape varieties, apart from Chardonnay where the two models are almost equally accurate (Table I). The higher recall of RCNN indicates its ability to identify a greater proportion of actual weeds, reducing the likelihood of missed detections. The SSD with ResNet101, while slightly less accurate, offers a faster and more computationally efficient alternative. However, this efficiency comes at the cost of reduced detection performance, particularly in terms of accuracy and F1-score. For inter-row weed detection, a PCL-ROS library is used to locate the weeds in the data (point cloud) collected from the vineyard. The developed model has been tested with promising results in fields with weeds in different growing stages [13].

Variety	RCNN	SSD
Sauvignon Blanc	0.9619	0.8735
Chardonnay	0.8898	0.8912
Malagouzia	0.8908	0.6221
Ksiniomauro	0.9565	0.7321
Syrah	0.9339	0.7025
Summary	0.9266	0.7643

TABLE I: Accuracy of weed detection models for grape varieties.

E. Crop Maturity Assessment

The quality of the crops is assessed in BACCHUS by the iMRP, using the Cubert FirefEYE V185 snapshot hyperspectral sensor. The sensor captures the visible-NIR region of 450-1000 nm with a spectral resolution of 4 nm while it follows specific SWaP (size, weight and power) requirements in order to be mounted on the iMRP. In terms of chemical composition, the aforementioned wavelength spectrum includes the important spectral information of the wine grapes that are the BACCHUS main use-case/application. The optimal distance from the grapes has been calculated to be 1.5 m based on the sensors' general specifications (i.e. field of view, lens angle, etc.). The specific amounts of certain chemical elements such as soluble solid content expressed in degrees Brix ($^{\circ}$ Brix), present in the grape, affect the spectral information. These concentrations absorb E/M radiation in small bands of the spectrum, necessitating the use of a camera with a large number of narrow spectral channels.

Before the operational use of the hyperspectral sensor on the iMRP, more than 300 hyperspectral cubes were captured on the field and a deep autoencoder framework [14] applied to transform the raw spectra into standardized reference spectra in order to address the impact of the in situ illumination conditions and shadowing effects on the spectral signal. A significant advantage of this technique is its ability to overcome the constant need for camera calibration using white reflectance panels in the field or the need of using any artificial light source for illumination control. The proposed methodology overcomes overheating problems and reduction in the sensor's response from continuous usage, enabling the mounting of the hyperspectral camera upon the iMRP, automating the monitoring process without any manual intervention from humans, contrary to existing works. The method's training data set was collected under different illumination conditions and various grape growing stages, thus there is no dependency on the initial sampling conditions. Nevertheless, the methodology is dependent on the utilized hyperspectral sensor and its strict specifications; in case a different sensor is used e.g. with different spectral bands, a new modelling process will be required to be built (e.g. with more or less input neurons) and the machine-learning model to be tailored to the new sensor's dataset. In 2023 summer period, a grape sampling was carried out for all the examined varieties (260 bunches) and an accredited laboratory analysis (OIV methods) including sugar content, pH and titratable acidity took place. Then, machine and deep learning algorithms are trained to build the optimal prediction model per variety providing the final decision for the bunch.

F. Gripper Design & Grasp Planning

This module involves the automated design regarding the gripper of the hMRP grasping arm, as well as the planning of pre-grasp and grasp poses, utilized in the grape bunch grasping during their harvesting (*Bimanual Control – Grape Harvesting module*).

1) *Automated Gripper Design Framework*: Visual data from the semantic segmentation sub-module and human demonstrations of the harvesting task are combined to create an initial gripper design that mimics the shape of human

Fig. 4: Top: BACCHUS automated gripper design GUI. Best-fitted fingertip design selected for target variety. Bottom: Collections of 3D pre-grasp & grasp poses for target grape bunch.

palms during harvesting. The goal is for the gripper to envelop the grape bunches in order to achieve more stable grasping and avoid slipping, without exerting high forces to the grape. Blender open-source software is used to create two highly parametric models for the gripper fingertips and grape bunches. By adjusting a variety of parameters, including overall bunch and individual berry dimensions, tension on the stem, berry roundness and girth, fingertip dimensions and curvature, as well as opening between fingertips, specialized gripper fingertips can be created for different grape varieties shapes and sizes. A custom graphical user interface has been developed (Figure 4 top row) to utilize the aforementioned models and guide the human operator through parameterization and simulation of grasping to evaluate the current gripper design in a user-friendly manner. The result is a customized gripper optimized for delicate grape handling and safe grasping, which can be quickly produced using additive manufacturing and be attached to the robotic arm for human-like harvesting.

2) *Grasp Planning Framework*: The grasp planning framework has been developed for automatically generating pre-grasp and grasp candidate poses. The process considers the gripper’s and grape bunch’s size and shape, and the grape variety. The grape bunch information, such as length and girth, is extracted from measuring its 2D mask. This information is then projected into 3D space to extract the 3D direction of the grape bunch with respect to the robotic platform using principal component analysis (PCA). This enables the gripper to approach the grape bunch perpendicularly to its dominant axis and achieve a stable grasp. In order to eliminate the angular error that may occur from PCA we consider the physical properties of grape bunches and the context of the task (bunches are always hanging by their stem, are close to being perpendicular to the ground, and their principal axis is along their length) to filter wrongful angles. The 3D point for grasping is calculated based on the size and calculated principal axis of the grape bunch. There, two concentric circles are generated, with their centers aligned to the computed 3D direction. The difference in the circles’ radii is derived from the length of the gripper fingertips. A collection of feasible grasping poses is then generated along the grasping

circles’ arc, by creating a pose every 2 degrees (accordingly for the pre-grasping circle/poses), which is an angle that is proved to be sufficient for generating feasible grasping poses by the low number of the failed cases that are attributed to grasping failures as reported in Section IV. These poses are then pruned and sorted based on the grape variety and gripper design, as well as semantic segmentation information of the surroundings, e.g. poses close to hard obstacles such as metallic poles have a lower ranking (Figure 4 bottom row).

G. Bimanual Control – Grape Harvesting

The BACCHUS harvesting procedure is executed according to the flowchart presented in Figure 5. After the hMRP arrives in front of the grape targeted for harvesting, the platform’s side camera scans for the target bunch. Once identified, the pre-grasp pose, calculated by the *Gripper Design & Grasp Planning* module, is reached by the grasping arm; this pose is utilized as an intermediate reaching goal to avoid undesired contact with the vine. Simultaneously, the camera arm reaches a Region Of Interest (ROI) close to the target grape, aligning its camera viewpoint towards the ROI center (centering), while visually unveiling the grape’s stem, from surrounding occlusions with respect to the in-hand camera. The latter is achieved via the control methodology proposed in [15]; this control scheme reaches the ROI progressively, unveiling the neighborhood of each visible point of the stem, by superimposing two body velocities for the camera arm’s end-effector (one for the reaching/centering for the camera arm and one for the unveiling task). Subsequently, the in-hand camera acquires the overall scene’s point-cloud and classifies it into grape bunch, associated stem and background/obstacles (i.e. everything else). Depending on the successful stem detection and visibility, the process then involves two distinct paths:

- The first path concerns the case where the stem is visible/unveiled and the pre-grasp pose has been successfully reached. The grasping arm reaches the final grasp pose (calculated by the *Gripper Design & Grasp Planning* module as well) and grasps the target bunch by closing its gripper. The grasped bunch is then manipulated, in order to maximize its stem-cutting affordances, with the

Fig. 5: BACCHUS harvesting procedure flowchart. Green colored: grasping arm tasks. Red colored: camera arm tasks.

camera arm keeping the stem visually unveiled. The implemented manipulation methodology [16] involves the scene’s point-cloud processing, the determination of the pull point residing in the largest free-space area around the stem taking also into account the cutter’s position, and a force/position controller that moves the grasped bunch towards the target free-space pull point while stretching its stem. The generated affordances are utilized for the easier cutter’s placement around it, which is performed via the visual servoing of the camera arm [17], [18]. After the stem is reached and cut, the grasped bunch is transferred to its storage location (red basket, Figure 1-(b)), with the gripper’s ability to sense if something is grasped being utilized to detect whether the bunch remains grasped during transfer.

- The second path regards the case when the stem is still not visible due to occlusions, after a visual unveiling action. The harvesting procedure then continues with the stem’s physical unveiling by the grasping arm, i.e. the arm moves aside the leaf/obstacle [19]. If the physical unveiling succeeds, making the target stem visible with respect to the camera arm, the procedure continues with a) the stem visual unveiling [15], in case of any remaining surrounding occlusions, b) the stem being reached by the open cutter [17], [18], c) the bunch’s grasping by the grasping arm and lastly d) the cutting of the stem. The detached grape is transferred to the storage location in the same manner as in the first path, completing the harvesting procedure.

Given the unstructured nature of the vineyard and aiming at the hMRP safe operation within the field, the robotic arms’ motion must respect multiple constraints, during harvesting. In BACCHUS, these constraints include joint limit avoid-

ance (position/velocity/acceleration constraints), self-collision avoidance (each arm with the other or both arms with the platform), obstacle collision avoidance (static/dynamic obstacles, e.g. humans moving in the robot’s workspace) and singularity avoidance. The BACCHUS implemented methodology for the satisfaction of the above safety constraints is presented in [20], which applies Hierarchical Quadratic Programming to generate the reference joint and mobile platform velocities, commanded to the robot (hMRP).

IV. BACCHUS IN-FIELD DEPLOYMENT AND RESULTS

The BACCHUS system has been excessively tested in the vineyard of Ktima Gerovassiliou, a wine producer, located in Thessaloniki, Greece. The testing environment consisted of 8 vine rows (about 40 m long) with each row containing approximately 40 vine trees. During the harvesting season of summer 2023, the system was deployed with the iMRP operating for 75 days for a total of over 300 hours and the hMRP operating for 62 days for a total of 248 hours.

The iMRP performed autonomously the grape detection and mapping, moving along the rows at about 10 cm/sec requiring 60 ms for grape detection per image. To assess the inspection platform’s effectiveness in crop mapping, 40 trials were carried out: 20 in a 40 m row of Monemvasia variety grapes (larger and denser grape bunches) with a detection success rate of 92.3% and 20 in a 40 m row of Priknadi variety grapes (smaller and sparser bunches) with a detection success rate of 94.6%. Throughout the 40 distinct trials, the iMRP estimated the grapes’ location relative to their trunk with a mean error of 5 cm (in 3d space), while detection failures occurred mainly due to the grape bunches being heavily occluded by leaves or other bunches.

The yield prediction system was also tested on 6 grape varieties in total, including Muscat of Alexandria, Malagouzia,

Fig. 6: BACCHUS visual interface. Apart from satellite vineyard overview with robots in-field location, production map can be viewed as heat-map (high-weight & ripe grape locations: red, low-weight & below-ripeness-threshold ones: green. Vineyard management panel is utilised for assigning tasks to workers, operations planning/monitoring, scheduling actions i.e. field irrigation, grape harvesting, yield prediction, removal of diseased/small grapes via elimination and thinning respectively (last two are the harvesting operation, but of diseased/small grapes instead of ripe ones). Side panel can change via View Settings option, visualising different objectives, e.g. providing weather data, monitoring yield estimation, getting live feedback from robot cameras, directly controlling robots for inspection/harvesting.

Fig. 7: BACCHUS harvesting process. (a) Initial state. Target grape detected by hMRP side camera. (b) Camera arm reaching & visually unveiling target stem while grasping arm reaches pre-grasp pose. (c) Grape grasped & manipulated for increasing its cutting affordances. (d) Stem stretched towards free-space (red dotted line). (e) Stem reached by cutter and cut. (f) Detached grape transferred into storage location.

Robola, Monemvasia, Priknadi, and Chardonnay, showing an average success rate of 92% with a yield underestimation error ranged between 3% and 9% depending on the variety, while counting grapes at approximately 0.05 minutes per meter. This error was due to either grape bunches' detection errors (ranging from 3.72% to 8.25% depending on the variety) or from estimation errors in the grape bunch weight-estimation regression models that utilize each detected bunch's segmented surface area (ranging from 0.34% to 1.3% depending on the variety). Moreover, the maturity level of 260 grape samples from chardonnay, malagouzia, sauvignon-blanc, and syrah varieties was estimated via the BACCHUS system, involving three different maturity level indicators i.e. sugar content (Brix), pH and titratable acidity; the system's estimation accuracy and more specifically the median Coefficient of Determination $R^2\%$ was above 75% for all 3 maturity level indicators (sugar content 77%, pH 75% and titratable acidity 76.5%).

The hMRP selective harvesting operation was also tested on multiple grape varieties (one row per variety). In a total of 95 grape bunches, the hMRP successfully harvested 71 of them, reaching a success rate of 74.7% and an approximate harvesting speed of 1 grape bunch per minute. The 24 total failures consisted of 6 grasping failures (wrong grasping pose calculation or grape slipping during harvesting) and 6 cases where the arms motion was stopped, due to contact of their end-effectors with the environment (e.g. irrigation pipes), leading to arm end-effectors contact forces exceeding a pre-set safety tolerance (6-7 N). The remaining failed cases included 5 stem detection failures (false negative detection), 4 cutting failures (wrong end-positioning of cutter upon stem), as well as 3 reaching failures where in order to perform the harvesting in cases of bunches with very short stems, the arms tips would have to get closer to each other than what the self-collision avoidance threshold allowed (thus their motion was stopped). From the successfully harvested grapes, only 4.5% of them were damaged, with a harvested bunch deemed as damaged if: 1) grasping was not maintained and the bunch fell from the gripper at any time during the whole process; 2) bunches came

in touch with anything (besides leaves) during their transfer; 3) cutter cut within the bunch damaging the grapes.

Comparison with human workers was also carried out showing that harvesting from experienced human workers lead to only 1% on damaged grapes with their harvesting error being negligible, compared to the 4.5% and 25.3% corresponding error rates of the BACCHUS system. However, these measurements of human performance did not concern selective harvesting, thus they cannot be directly comparable with the added value that BACCHUS can provide. Concerning yield prediction, manual prediction errors varied between 13% to 16% depending on grape variety, while BACCHUS achieved a 92% accuracy, maintaining a consistent estimation error of approximately 8%, regardless of variety.

Figures 6 - 8 present results from the system's deployment. Specifically, Figure 6 shows a detailed description of the visual interface (*Visualization & GUI* module). The iMRP

Fig. 8: BACCHUS grape maturity detection. Top: Matching of images from iMRP hyperspectral and ZED2i side camera for crop mapping. Bottom: Grape maturity detection/ripeness estimation. First left image: initial bunch detection - green, buffer zone area - white.

side ZED2i camera detected the grape bunches, while its Hyperspectral camera was responsible for extracting the spectra signature and providing the final ripeness estimation per bunch (Figure 8). At this point and regarding the grape bunch detection process, it should be emphasized that a buffer zone (smaller than the initial bunch detection area) was created, in order to exclude the border region of the bunch and to avoid any pixels that might include out-of-bunch information, creating noise and affecting the final estimation. Having identified and mapped the bunches ready for harvesting based on their maturity level, the hMRP was then sent to harvest a specific crop, chosen by the human operator. Figure 7 presents the harvesting procedure, that involved the grasping of the target grape (Figure 7-(b)), its manipulation to increase its stem cutting affordances (Figure 7, (c)-(d)) and finally the cutting tool's placement upon the stem via visual servoing (Figure 7, (e)-(f)). A video from the overall system's operation can be found in the following link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V2Yqa_9R1JU.

V. CONCLUSION

BACCHUS project has developed an innovative and complete agricultural robotic solution regarding the high-value crop of grapes, coupling inspection functionalities with that of selective harvesting. The developed system comprises two independent and cooperative robotic platforms, equipped with enhanced sensing capabilities that can navigate in heterogeneous agricultural areas of various slopes. All BACCHUS operations were extensively tested and evaluated in a wine grape vineyard achieving: a) high success rates of over 92% for the grape detection and yield prediction; b) a median Coefficient of Determination above 75% for all 3 maturity level indicators that were taken into consideration, specifically sugar content (Brix), PH and titratable acidity and c) a success rate of 75% in grape harvesting under challenging conditions comprising among others semi or fully occluded stems and/or stems without free space around them to place the cutter. With the developed novel control methodologies and machine learning algorithms and the human-inspired, bi-manual harvesting operations, the BACCHUS system is pioneering in the application of agricultural robotics in the relatively under-explored area of selective harvesting of delicate crops such as grapes.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research received funding from the European Community's Framework Programme Horizon 2020 under grant agreement No 871704, project BACCHUS.

REFERENCES

[1] L. Droukas, Z. Doulgeri, N. L. Tsakiridis, D. Triantafyllou, I. Kleitsiotis, I. Mariolis, D. Giakoumis, D. Tzovaras, D. Kateris, and D. Bochtis, "A survey of robotic harvesting systems and enabling technologies." *J Intell Robot Syst*, vol. 107, no. 21, Jan. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10846-022-01793-z>

[2] J. Chagas and M. Wagner, "Efficiently solving the thief orienteering problem with a max-min ant colony optimization approach," in *Optimization Letters*, 2022, pp. 2313—2331.

[3] J. P. Fentanes, B. Lacerda, T. Krajník, N. Hawes, and M. Hanheide, "Now or later? predicting and maximising success of navigation actions from long-term experience," in *2015 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2015, pp. 1112–1117.

[4] S. Molina, G. Cielniak, and M. Hanheide, "Uav-assisted topological mapping for agv navigation in vineyards," in *ICRA 2022 Workshop on Agricultural Robotics and Automation*, 2022.

[5] I. Hroob, S. Molina, R. Polvara, G. Cielniak, and M. Hanheide, "Lts-net: End-to-end unsupervised learning of long-term 3d stable objects," in *Intelligent Autonomous Systems 18*. Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 17–29, doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-44981-9_2.

[6] C. R. Qi, L. Yi, H. Su, and L. J. Guibas, "Pointnet++: Deep hierarchical feature learning on point sets in a metric space," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 30, 2017.

[7] R. Polvara, S. Molina, I. Hroob, A. Papadimitriou, K. Tsiolis, D. Giakoumis, S. Likothanassis, D. Tzovaras, G. Cielniak, and M. Hanheide, "Bacchus long-term (blt) data set: Acquisition of the agricultural multimodal blt data set with automated robot deployment," *Journal of Field Robotics*, 2023.

[8] W. Xu and F. Zhang, "Fast-lio: A fast, robust lidar-inertial odometry package by tightly-coupled iterated kalman filter," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 3317–3324, 2021.

[9] A. Papadimitriou, I. Kleitsiotis, I. Kostavelis, I. Mariolis, D. Giakoumis, S. Likothanassis, and D. Tzovaras, "Loop closure detection and slam in vineyards with deep semantic cues," in *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 2251–2258.

[10] K. He, G. Gkioxari, P. Dollár, and R. Girshick, "Mask r-cnn," in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, 2017, pp. 2961–2969.

[11] I. Kleitsiotis, I. Mariolis, D. Giakoumis, S. Likothanassis, and D. Tzovaras, "Anisotropic diffusion-based enhancement of scene segmentation with instance labels," in *Computer Analysis of Images and Patterns: 19th International Conference, CAIP 2021, Virtual Event, September 28–30, 2021, Proceedings, Part II 19*. Springer, 2021, pp. 383–391.

[12] V. Moysiadis, D. Kateris, D. Katikaridis, G. Vasileiadis, V. Kolorizos, A. C. Tagarakis, and D. Bochtis, "A real-time approach system for vineyards intra-row weed detection," in *10th HAICTA International Conference on Information & Communication Technologies in Agriculture, Food and Environment*, 2022, pp. 39–44. [Online]. Available: <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3293/paper14.pdf>

[13] D. Kateris, D. Kalaitzidis, V. Moysiadis, A. C. Tagarakis, and D. Bochtis, "Weed mapping in vineyards using rgb-d perception," *Engineering Proceedings*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/engproc2021009030>

[14] N. L. Tsakiridis, N. Samarinas, S. Kokkas, E. Kalopesa, N. V. Tziolas, and G. C. Zalidis, "In situ grape ripeness estimation via hyperspectral imaging and deep autoencoders," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 212, p. 108098, Sep. 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2023.108098>

[15] D. Papageorgiou, L. Koutras, and Z. Doulgeri, "A controller for reaching and unveiling a partially occluded object of interest with an eye-in-hand robot," in *2022 IEEE-RAS 21st International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids)*, 2022, pp. 254–260. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/Humanoids53995.2022.10000171>

[16] S. Stavridis, L. Droukas, and Z. Doulgeri, "Bimanual grape manipulation for human-inspired robotic harvesting," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, pp. 1–11, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMECH.2024.3459479>

[17] P. D. Triantafyllou, G. A. Rovithakis, and Z. Doulgeri, "Constrained visual servoing under uncertain dynamics," *International Journal of Control*, vol. 92, no. 9, pp. 2099–2111, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207179.2018.1428362>

[18] A. P. Kechagias and G. A. Rovithakis, "Achieving prescribed performance for euler-lagrange systems with impulsive behaviour," in *2022 30th Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED)*, 2022, pp. 97–102. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MED54222.2022.9837127>

[19] A. Sidiropoulos and Z. Doulgeri, "From rgb images to dynamic movement primitives for planar tasks," in *2023 IEEE-RAS 22nd International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids)*, 2023, pp. 1–8. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/Humanoids57100.2023.10375217>

[20] S. Stavridis, P. Falco, and Z. Doulgeri, "Pick-and-place in dynamic environments with a mobile dual-arm robot equipped with distributed distance sensors," in *2020 IEEE-RAS 20th International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids)*, 2021, pp. 76–82. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/HUMANOIDS47582.2021.9555672>